

BASIC CONDITIONS OF LABOR PROTECTION IN LANDSCAPING WORKS

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Abstract. *This article theoretically analyzes the legal basis of organizing labor protection works, organizational and technical measures that serve to implement labor relations between the employer and the employee, and the main conditions for organizing labor protection works of workers engaged in beautification and landscaping works.*

Keywords: *labor protection, workplace, harmful factors, accidents, injury, work at height.*

Introduction. It is known that a number of studies have been carried out by scientists and specialists of different countries on issues of labor protection of employees of all economic sectors. Scientists and researchers of Uzbekistan and foreign countries conducted scientific research aimed at analyzing and improving the working conditions of their employees and developed a number of noteworthy practical solutions and recommendations. As a result of creation and introduction of ergonomic, sanitary-hygienic requirements for workplaces and their equipment, the dynamics of accidents and occupational diseases will be reduced.

Literature analysis and methodology. During the studies [1], due to the weight and stress of the labor process of the workers engaged in landscaping work, the bending and working position of the body during the shift was not fully studied, and no specific technical solution was given in terms of ergonomic [2] parameters, and the harmful factor of production (dust and car exhaust gas) appeared. The sources and routes of transmission are not fully understood. A practical technical solution to reduce this has not been developed[3].

It is known that ensuring the safety, life and health of workers during the work process, as well as the ability to work, is of great socio-economic importance. If workers' working conditions meet hygienic requirements, their safety is ensured and labor productivity is high.

The results of the study, systematization and critical analysis of the scientific work aimed at improving the safety of the workers engaged in landscaping work showed that a number of scientific studies have been conducted and are being conducted by domestic and foreign scientists and researchers in this direction. Based on the results of scientific research, various methods and tools for improving the safety of working conditions have been developed and introduced into production.

Several principles and methods of ensuring it are used in the practice of labor protection. Recommendations and tools developed based on the results of research are created within the framework of these principles and methods. Constructive, organizational and material implementation of principles and methods is an expression of labor protection. Labor protection can be divided into guiding, technical, organizational and management principles. Changing technology, replacing harmful substances with safe substances, using safe equipment and improving the scientific organization of work are the guiding principles for the elimination of harmful and dangerous factors. Protection of a person from a distance, which provides a certain

level of safety, setting such a distance between a person and the source of danger, guaranteeing protection from danger by installing a barrier between the source of danger and a person are technical principles. The principles of reducing the dangerous values of the duration of people's stay in the conditions of exposure to risk, compensation, health restoration, prevention of diseases, giving benefits are organizational. Selection of personnel, professional knowledge, skills, experience, specialists, incentives, qualitative and quantitative indicators, moral and material incentives are management principles.

Results. As research, the legal basis of organizing labor protection works, organizational and technical measures that serve to implement labor relations between the employer and employee, the main conditions for organizing labor protection works of workers engaged in landscaping works, Surkhondarya region Termiz for theoretical analysis The employees of the city and Zharkurgan District Improvement Department were selected.

The total number of employees of the Department of Improvement of the city of Termiz is 454 people. 227 (49%) of them are men, 233 (51%) are women (see Figure 1).

51% women (233 people), 49% men (227 people)

Figure 1. The number of employees of the Department of Improvement of the city of Termiz.

The total number of employees of the Department of Improvement of Jarkurgan district is 175 people. 47 (27%) of them are women, 128 (73%) are men (see Figure 2).

27% women (47 people), 73% men (128 people)

Figure 2. The number of employees of the Department of Improvement of Jarkurgan district.

Occupational safety is not only the health of workers, but also a powerful economic factor, because the improvement of working conditions leads to increased labor productivity, longer service life of equipment, reduction of occupational sick leave payments, disability benefits, etc.

The economic effect of the implementation of labor protection measures depends on the following indicators of production activity:

- increase in labor productivity;
- reducing the complexity of products;
- reduction of losses related to injuries and occupational diseases;
- reduction of staff turnover;
- increasing the professional activity of the worker;
- increase the efficiency of equipment use;
- reduction of benefits and compensation costs.

It has been scientifically proven that reasonable measures aimed at increasing the safety of working conditions lead to increased labor productivity (see Table 1). When calculating or predicting the effectiveness of measures to improve the safety of working conditions, the connection between the planned measures and economic ones is established.

Table 1

Indicators of measures to improve the safety of working conditions

№	Name of measures	Growth Efficiency %
1	Reduce noise to acceptable standards	3-15
2	Smart coloring of the room	up to 25
3	Use music wisely	12-14
4	Creating stable lighting	10-15
5	proper organization of the workplace	up to 20
6	A drop in air temperature	From 18 to 50

Discussions. In addition to the above points, it can be said that ensuring the optimal level of work mode and rest of employees is achieved through:

- identification of workplaces and sections with harmful working conditions;
- compliance with the established regime of work and rest;
- providing work and rest regimes that ensure high efficiency of workers;
- taking breaks from work or providing temporary stoppage of work based on wind strength and outside air temperature;

depending on the wind force and outside air temperature, it is necessary to take breaks in work or to ensure temporary stoppage of work;

based on working conditions, it is necessary to determine the contingent of employees to whom compensation payments and benefits are provided for harmful working conditions and provide them with these benefits.

State control over the observance of labor protection legislation and these Rules based on the rules of labor protection in landscaping works is carried out by specially authorized state agencies, and public control is carried out by labor protection representatives elected by labor groups and trade unions.

In accordance with the Model Regulation "On Organization of Labor Protection" (Register No. 273, August 14, 1996), the following should be controlled in enterprises:

- the state of workplaces;
- compliance with labor legislation;
- timely and correct investigation of accidents;
- proper spending of funds allocated for labor protection;
- implementation of labor protection measures and others.

In accordance with Article 12 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Labor Protection", labor protection service is organized from among specially trained persons in enterprises with 50 or more employees. In enterprises with less than 50 employees, the performance of labor protection functions is entrusted to one of the heads of the enterprise.

In accordance with the requirements of the regulation "On the development of labor protection guidelines" (list number 870, January 7, 2000), it is necessary to develop and approve separate labor protection guidelines for each specialty, as well as for each type of work.

The dangerous and harmful production factors that affect employees in enterprises, causing injury, illness or reduced work capacity, are:

- works carried out near working power transmission lines;
- Excavation works in the sections where live electric cables are laid;
- carrying out work related to the transportation of chlorine, the use of chlorine and other highly toxic substances;
- carrying out work related to the use and release of fluorine;
- Excavation works on the pathogen-infested areas of the land (waste collection sites, cattle mortuaries, graves and other similar places);
- performing work at height and performing work related to climbing at height;
- carrying out work related to cutting trees;
- carry out work related to loading, unloading and primary processing of trees onto vehicles;
- during the movement of vehicles, to saturate trees with antiseptic and fire protection products in traffic areas.

Conclusions.

Using the principles and methods of ensuring labor protection to improve the working conditions of the employees of the Department of Land Improvement, in-depth theoretical and practical analysis of the results of certification of workplaces, the sources of harmful and dangerous production factors, the causes of their occurrence, and the quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the parameters of the severity and strain of workers' labor is appropriate.

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